

EXERCISES DESIGNED TO GROW THE ORAL AND WRITTEN SPEECH OF STUDENTS

Trainee teacher, Jizzakh State Pedagogical University

Turanazarova Nilufar Raxmonqul qizi

Student of the primary education direction

Saydullayeva Shaxzoda

Jizzakh, Uzbekistan

Tel: +998(33) 310-00-26

turanazarovanilufar@gmail.com

Annotation

This article talks about teaching students to practice the specific features of the conditions and procedures for the use of exercises and methods designed to develop oral and written speech based on theoretical information.

Keyword: Speech, oral and written speech, story, text, monologue speech, style of speech, artistic work.

It is important that the growth of the student's speech is a systematic and continuous process, being able to independently interpret the free assignments given by the teacher, to be able to reflect the concepts in the imagination in the process of completing the assignment, but the understanding that the student receives from the text can be different from the obvious instruction given to Thinking grows, relying on each of the conclusions made by readers – This forms the basis of the development of written and oral speech. Nevertheless, the teacher needs to focus on information that is formed on specific conditions and guidelines so that students can improve their speech skills, visualize thoughts in a lively way and complete a given task. Various exercises are also envisaged for oral and written speech, as well as for communicating the awareness of the reader from the principles of speech.

In conclusion, the periodic development of speech knowledge and competencies of students, the ways of its improvement are a complex research work that illuminates the understandable and detailed classification, since it covers in detail the possibilities of a separate or entire language.

It is no secret that in many cases the use of texts in the cultivation of oral speech has become a tradition. But choosing a free text based on the age and potential of the student

requires special attention from the teacher. Let's cite an example of tasks that can be performed on the basis of text and text as evidence of our ideas, which are now presented below.

” The unskilled man is near death " is an Uzbek folk tale.

The unskilled man is near death

It turns out that a king lived in the past time. One day he went hunting and fell in love with the beautiful daughter of a carpenter there.

To the suitors who came by the King:

-- What is your king's craft, I marry someone with crafts?- girl.

Suitors:

- Will there be a greater craft in the world than the kingdom? The king will be the father of all the skilled, " they said.

Girl:

-I do not need the father of the artisan, I need the artisan himself. With the change of times, the one who is the king today can remain a beggar tomorrow. Go and tell your king, let him show me his craft, after which I touch.

The suitors come back and say the girl's answer. The King's bitterness at these words meant to punish the girl, but his love for the girl did not allow it.

Not knowing what to do, he was on a board with a teacher who taught himself. The teacher quoted "seventy new trades" and read it out of sound. From one place came out the words "the unskilled man is near death". The teacher also closed the book here:

"The girl has the right to say, "I touch her craft."

Another thousand sorrows were added to the earlier pain of the King. He gave permission to the teacher, but made a covenant to learn a trade on his own. The next day, while sitting on the throne of the King, a man brought a rug. When the carpet was seen, the King was in the mood to learn how to weave the carpet. He begged me to teach the carpet. He taught the king his profession for twenty-five days. Having prepared the necessary things, the King made a carpet with his own hands and gave it to the carpenter's daughter from the suitors. When the suitors showed the girl the carpet that the King had woven with his own hands, she:

- Now the king is the one I want, go and say, let him start the wedding.

Now answer the questions asked on the basis of the assignment.

You will need to read the stories and articles before completing this task. The questions in the assignment refer to the text you read. Some questions may seem easier

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and some more difficult, but when answering any question, try to formulate a certain specific and logical answer in your mind. Some questions are given 4 answer options, mark the letter in which you are right to gather your opinion.

The first example presents such a question and also shows how to answer it correctly.

1. Whose daughter was the girl the King liked?

- A) merchant.
- B) farmer.
- C) Woodman.
- D) fisherman.

2. What kind of person does a girl need ?

- A) a military officer from martial arts.
- B) honourable.
- C) hardworking.
- D) wealthy.

3. What caused the king to add pain to his pain?

1. _____

4. Who was responsible for the craft that the king fell for?

1. _____

5. The girl told the suitors for what work the king would start the wedding?

- A) for trying to punish the girl.
- B) for giving a carpet.
- C) for throwing his father into the dungeon.
- D) for taking the century.

6. What made the king come to the conclusion that death drove me here? express the answer in 2 situations.

1. _____

2. _____

7. How many days does the King ask for respite from the people of kabobchi?

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- (A) 25
- B) 40
- C) 30
- D) 20

8. What do you think the king aimed at by saying his craft?

1. _____

9. Who does the King say to pull the carpet?

- A) to my wife.
- B) to ministers.
- C) to the King.
- D) to the poor.

10. What sign did the king leave on the carpet?

- A) left a hole.
- B) left a seal.
- C) drew a map of the dungeon.
- D) asked for help.

11. To whom did kabobchi's people give the carpet?

- A) to the minister.
- B) to the guard.
- C) to the Queen.
- D) to the minister.

12. Who saw the seal from which the king fell?

- A) minister.
- B) daughter of a carpenter.
- C) guards.
- D) passenger.

13. What caused the king to learn a trade?

Write down the reason why the king decides to learn a craft, and to confirm your answer, separate from the text the sentences with the corresponding example.

14. What saved him from the craft learned by the King? Understand your answer using the information in the story.

1. _____

15. What do you think, would the craft you learned to the King help even later?

1. _____

16. What is the role of the craft in people's lives? You know what trades he needs everyone. What craft do you love yourself and why.

Give one reason.

1. _____

In conclusion, in recent years, the identification of students ' reading and understanding skills, relying on international assessment programs such as PIRLS, TIMSS, TALIS, EGRA, EGMA and the like, has been introduced in the educational system of our country. It is in view of the fact that, relying on memory as part of reading literacy among the primary classes after the International Assessment Program of PISA, it led to the emergence of discussions that it is not effective for students to be evaluated by answering text-based questions after getting acquainted with the text, working with the text and answering, it has also been found that the reader's reading and comprehension skills are mixed with the memory retention skills. Of course, this aspect of Reading Literacy in the program is also taken into account. It would not be a mistake to say that the cultivation of oral and written speech, on the basis of similar problems in elementary grades, is the key to obtaining all knowledge and having positive results. Speech cultivation is the work on a word; work on a word combination and a sentence; separated into directions such as work on linked speech. Lexicology (together with phraseology and Stylistics), morphology, siintaxic serve as the linguistic base for working on words, vocabulary and sentence; while linked speech is based on logic, literary studies and complex syntactic whole linguistics.

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